

Charge and Stability of Colloids. Part XXIV. Effect of Dilution on the Displacement of Chloride Ions from Fe_2O_3 Sol

B. P. Yadava and M. Yaseen

Ferric hydroxide sol has been coagulated at a particular concentration by adding varying amounts of anions of different valencies and the release of counter ions determined potentiometrically. Similar observations have been made with the same sol, diluted to half and to one-fourth of its concentration respectively. The amount of chloride ions displaced from the original sol has been found greater than the one which is released from that diluted to half its concentration of the same sol, when both are coagulated by a certain amount of anions of same valency. The amount of chloride ions displaced from the sol goes on decreasing on further dilution of the sol.

The inner portion of the double layer of Fe_2O_3 sol consists of Fe^{3+} and H^+ ions in the adsorption equilibrium with the corresponding anions in the intermicellar liquid. The outer portion consists of diffused layer of chloride ions, most of which are held by electrostatic attraction of the adsorbed inner layer. A part of the latter, on account of relatively high kinetic energy, exerts sufficient osmotic repulsive force against the attraction of the double layer to influence the calomel electrode and it may be detected potentiometrically¹. In the coagulation of sols formed by FeCl_3 , the precipitating anion is taken up by particle in exchange with chloride ions². Earlier workers³⁻⁵ studied potentiometrically the change in chloride-ion concentration by stepwise addition of anions to hydroxide sols. It is found that Burton's rule is not generally applicable to many sols, specially those of hydroxides. Weiser and Nicholas⁶ observed that the precipitation value decreased with decreasing concentration of ferric oxide sol and the decrease was proportional to its concentration in the case of multivalent ions⁷. The precipitation value of potassium chloride actually increases with dilution of negative arsenic trisulphide⁸ and even of very highly purified Fe_2O_3 ⁹.

EXPERIMENTAL

The Fe_2O_3 sol was prepared as in a previous communication⁵ and it was treated as original sol. Experiments were carried out on original sol, on half, and on one-fourth of

1. Pauli *et al.*, *Kolloid Z.*, 1917, 21, 54; 1924, 35, 133; *Koll.-Chem. Beih.*, 1923, 17, 256.
2. Weiser and Gray, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1932, 36, 2178.
3. Rabinovich *et al.*, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1928, A133, 203; 1932, A159, 403.
4. Weiser, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1931, 35, 1.
5. Yadava, *this Journal*, 1943, 20, 115, 123, 199.
6. *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1921, 25, 742.
7. Takamatsu, *Kolloid Z.*, 1926, 38, 229.
8. Burton and Bishop, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1920, 24, 701.
9. Sorum, *Kolloid Z.*, 1932, 58, 314.

its concentration. The sol and electrolyte mixtures were prepared by taking a constant volume (5 ml) of the sol and varying concentrations of electrolyte, keeping a constant total volume of 10 ml in each bottle. To each of these bottles small doses of pure calomel were added and mixtures were left for 24 hours to attain equilibrium. With the help of half elements the resulting potential of the sol and electrolyte mixtures was determined against a standard *N/10* calomel electrode. The modified form of the Nernst equation was used to calculate the activity of the displaced chloride ions. This calculated value of activity was converted into molar concentration on dividing it by the activity coefficient as read from the graph obtained from the data of Lewis and Randall¹⁰. The amount of electrolyte added is expressed in terms of the equivalent of chloride ions displaced. The displacement of chloride ions was studied by coagulating the sol by varying concentrations of KNO_3 , KIO_3 , K_2SO_4 , and K -citrate.

TABLE I

Conc. of original Fe_2O_3 sol = 7.68 g./litre. Total vol. of sol (5 ml) + electrolyte solns. + water = 10 ml.

Electrolyte soln.	(Cl ⁻) × 10 ³ displaced.		
	Original sol.	$\frac{1}{2}$ Origl. sol.	$\frac{1}{4}$ Origl. sol.
0.2 <i>N</i> - KNO_3 soln.			
0.0 ml	0.00 g. equiv.	0.00 g. equiv.	0.00 g. equiv.
0.5	2.54	1.65	0.88
1.0	4.24	2.96	2.07
1.5	5.09	3.80	2.85
2.0	6.41	4.50	3.40
2.5	8.28	5.67	3.88
3.0	8.66	6.44	4.59
0.2 <i>N</i> - KIO_3 soln.			
0.5	3.04	1.87	1.25
1.0	4.96	2.72	2.45
1.5	6.41	4.10	3.04
2.0	8.42	4.60	3.60
2.5	8.08	5.51	4.04
3.0	9.25	6.49	4.62
0.04 <i>N</i> - K_2SO_4 soln.			
0.5	3.35	2.55	1.53
1.0	5.23	3.32	2.87
1.5	7.01	4.66	3.83
2.0	8.55	5.80	4.83
2.5	10.08	7.53	5.94
3.0	11.10	8.28	6.28
0.04 <i>N</i> - K citrate soln.			
0.5	3.67	2.90	1.92
1.0	5.71	3.89	2.91
1.5	7.83	4.90	4.80
2.0	9.69	5.66	6.08
2.5	10.43	7.60	6.87
3.0	12.07	9.59	7.02

10. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 43, 1132.

DISCUSSION

In the initial stage of coagulation, 10.0×10^{-3} g. equiv. of nitrate ions are found to displace 2.54×10^{-3} g. equiv. of chloride ions, whereas 2.0×10^{-3} g. equiv. sulphate and citrate ions are able to displace 3.25×10^{-3} and 3.67×10^{-3} g. equiv. of chloride ions respectively from Fe_2O_3 sol. The release of chloride ions goes on increasing by raising the concentration of the electrolyte, but the rate of displacement is not regular with the regular increase of the concentration of electrolyte. The displaceable chloride ion content of Fe_2O_3 sol decreases with its dilution. It is found that 10.0×10^{-3} g. equiv. of nitrate ions displaces 2.54×10^{-3} g. equiv. of chloride ions from original sol and the same amount of these ions displaces 1.65×10^{-3} and 0.88×10^{-3} g. equiv. of chloride ions from half and one-fourth concentrations of the original sol respectively. The bivalent and trivalent coagulating ions show a similar effect with the dilution of sol, i.e., 2×10^{-3} g. equiv. of sulphate ions displaces 3.25×10^{-3} , 2.55×10^{-3} , and 1.53×10^{-3} g. equiv. of chloride ions from original sol and its half and one-fourth concentrations. The same amount of citrate ions displaces 3.67×10^{-3} , 2.90×10^{-3} , and 1.92×10^{-3} g. equiv. of chloride ions from the above concentrations of the sol.

It is obvious from these data that the displacement of chloride ions from Fe_2O_3 sol by a particular amount of a coagulating ion is in increasing order with the dilution of the sol. In the case of univalent coagulating ions, the displacement of chloride ions is not remarkably high as it is in the case of bivalent and trivalent ions. The amount of chloride ions displaced from half of the original sol by a certain amount of sulphate ions is considerably greater than the half of the chloride ions displaced from the original sol by the same amount of sulphate ions. Similar data have been found when sols of different concentrations are coagulated by citrate ions.

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